

Dynamic Real-World Measurements of Light-Mediated Changes in Pupil Size

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1 Abstract

Purpose: With the recent development of lightweight, high-resolution spectroradiometers, meeting the demands for more ecologically valid light research has become more viable. Here, we demonstrate a novel method to assess the light inputs regulating pupil size under dynamic real-world conditions.

Background: Pupil size modulates light incident on the retina and is applied as a versatile, non-invasive biomarker for both visual and non-visual processing in humans. Steady-state pupil diameter is largely determined by the activity of the intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs) expressing the short-wavelength-sensitive photopigment melanopsin ($\lambda_{\max} = 480$ nm), which provides a light-sensitive pathway in addition to the canonical photoreceptors, the rods and cones. From tightly controlled laboratory studies employing parametric stimuli, we know that melanopic radiance drives pupil size, with higher melanopic radiance associated with a smaller pupil diameter. At present, there is no established method or data set assessing variations in pupil size in real-world light exposure.

Methods: A wearable infrared video-based eye tracker (Pupil Labs GmbH) was integrated with a small-scale spectroradiometer (Ocean Insight STS-Vis, wavelength accuracy: ± 0.13 nm, optical resolution: 6 nm with 100 μm slit) and attached to a bespoke 3D-printed and adjustable head mount. Both devices were connected to a miniature, battery-driven control computer (Raspberry Pi), thereby enabling joint simultaneous sampling of pupil diameter and spectral irradiance in the near-corneal plane at 10-sec intervals. In a total of seven healthy participants ($n = 7$; age range: 20-30 years), we measured natural variation in pupil size and eye-level light exposure across two protocols, in which participants moved in and between indoor and outdoor environments, varying

in light conditions, and engaged in a range of everyday tasks. The spectral samples were subjected to a dark- and thermal noise calibration using a polynomial noise estimation model derived from a collected dark spectra database. Melanopic irradiance and photopic lux values were then calculated from the calibrated spectra using the respective standardised CIE spectral sensitivity curves. Absolute pupil diameter was estimated from raw images using a calibrated 3D pupil model.

Results: We successfully assessed variation in pupil size as a function of near-corneal melanopic irradiance in the real world, yielding distinct dose-response curves for each participant. Data retention was considerably high under these dynamic uncontrolled conditions (~65% data retained; total number of usable spectrum and pupil size pairs: 6620). The dark and thermal noise calibration reduced deviations in the spectral data to a reasonable level of ≤ 1 lux.

Conclusions: In summary, we demonstrate a robust portable system for measuring eye-level light exposure and physiological signals in humans under dynamic real-world conditions. In the future, this set-up will be used to address real-world light and pupil assessment in a wide range of research questions and use-cases.

2 Introduction

Our visual system depends on light entering the eye and exciting the retinal photoreceptors. Acting as a gatekeeper, our pupil can regulate the amount of incoming light by constricting and dilating within a limited range (~2 to ~8 mm diameter) [1, 2]. This regulation of pupil size is essential for optimising the retinal image [3–7], while also modulating non-visual processes like the entrainment of circadian rhythms to external light-dark cycles and melatonin suppression in response to light [8, 9].

To date, our knowledge of pupil size almost exclusively stems from controlled laboratory studies using simplified parametric stimuli. This body of well-controlled research has shown that all five photoreceptor types contribute to the control of the pupil, though their spatial and temporal contributions are different [10]. Converging evidence suggests that steady-state pupil size in photopic light levels is mainly regulated by the melanopsin-encoded signal ($\lambda_{\max} = 480$ nm), stemming from the intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs) [10–14]. As pupil size is a crucial factor for visual and non-visual functioning in real life, relying solely on data limited to laboratory settings will not lead to a comprehensive understanding of the pupillary light response in a complex multi-variate world [15]. Meanwhile, with the recent development of lightweight and portable spectroradiometers and eye-tracking devices, meeting

the demands for more ecologically valid research has become more viable in this field. However, moving research into the field gives rise to a new set of challenges [16]. Here, we demonstrate a newly developed system for assessing the light inputs regulating pupil size under dynamic real-world conditions and provide an in-depth description of tackling a common challenge for spectroradiometric measurements, namely their dark and thermal noise calibration.

3 Methods

3.1 Spectroradiometric Measurements

We recorded the irradiance spectrum in the approximate corneal plane with a research-grade commercial small-footprint spectroradiometer (STS-VIS, Ocean Insight Inc., Oxford, UK; cf. Fig. 1 A & B), equipped with a direct-attach cosine corrector (CC-3-DA, diameter: 7140 μm , 180° field of view). The spectroradiometer is wavelength-calibrated in the range of 350–800 nm with a wavelength accuracy of ± 0.13 nm and optical resolution of 6 nm (100 μm slit). The STS measures with a signal-to-noise ratio of >1500:1 and a dynamic range of 4600:1. We pre-set the Integration times to range from 10 μsec –5 sec.

A customised 3D-printed case enclosed the spectroradiometer (see Fig. 1 C) designed and fabricated in collaboration with digitalwerkstatt GmbH in Basel, Switzerland. The case is adjustable in angle and mounted on a wearable, padded headband, which can be adapted to different head sizes. We designed the case's connective joint to match typical action camera accessories to allow for the versatile use of low-cost replacement accessories. The mount was centred on the forehead, such that it was approximately conjoint with the corneal plane and in the approximate direction of gaze of the observer. The vertical angle of the spectroradiometer's diffuser is set pointing 15° below the horizontal at default for every participant, corresponding to typical outdoor gaze angle [17]. Irradiance spectra were measured every 10 sec and stored on a custom-made, portable Raspberry Pi-based microcontroller (in .csv format), along with the corresponding integration time and board temperature values, measured by internal sensors. Temperature and integration time values were later used in the dark and thermal noise calibration.

3.2 Pupil Size Measurements

An infrared video-based "Pupil Core" eye-tracker (Pupil Labs GmbH, Berlin, DE; cf. Fig. 1 A & B) was used to collect still photographs of the participant's pupil at the same time as the irradiance spectra. Images from the camera were polled using OpenCV and stored on the same on the Raspberry Pi-based microcontroller as the spectroradiometric measurements. Embedded

programming on the microcontroller was provided by Ocean Insight Inc. engineering. The still photographs were later subjected to a 3D model, estimated during a calibration procedure supplied by the eye tracker manufacturer [18]. The 3D model [19] assumes that the 3D pupil can be modelled as disk, which in each moment is tangent to a rotating eye sphere. Elliptic pupil contours are extracted using a pupil segmentation algorithm and the centre of the eye sphere is estimated using a nonlinear optimisation procedure. A 3-min pupil calibration video was recorded as part of the preparation procedure immediately before experimental sampling to obtain an accurate eye model.

Fig.1: Wearable, portable device for joint measurements of pupil size and near-corneal irradiance. A Glass head showing the ambulatory measurement set-up incorporating the infra-red eye tracker, spectroradiometer, control computer (Raspberry Pi) and a power bank (first design). **B** Improved set-up used in the experiments. **C.** Angled customised 3D-printed spectroradiometer case.

3.3 Dark and Thermal Noise Spectroradiometer Calibration

Spectroradiometric measurements are biased by noise [20]. To remedy this issue, some spectroradiometers subtract a corresponding, shutter-generated

dark spectrum from every collected spectral sample. As the small-scale STS spectrometer lacks such a shutter mechanism, a calibration had to be applied by software after data collection. We found the magnitude of noise in each spectral sample to be dependent on the spectroradiometer's board temperature at that point in time and the integration time (span) used to collect that sample. More specifically, the noise across wavelength pixels increased with higher temperature and higher integration time (see Fig. 2). While the utilised integration time for a sample is determined by light intensity – longer integration times used in darkness, shorter integration times in bright light – the board temperature usually rises in the course of a sampling session. Our goal was to devise a reliable model, which predicts “noise counts” [Z in number of sensor counts] from board temperature measured by an internal sensor [X in °C] and integration time [Y in ms]. This was carried out as described below, resembling the calibration procedure by [20].

Dark Spectra Database (Training Dataset):

A series of dark spectra measurements was collected with a plastic cap covering the spectroradiometer's light sensor, incorporating different board temperatures and integration times in the range of our experimental conditions. The measurements were executed with OceanView 2.0 software (Ocean Insight Inc., Oxford, UK) on a Windows-10-based Laptop, controlling the STS-VIS spectroradiometer. Six separate 60-minute sampling sessions were carried out, each corresponding to a pre-set integration time (10 ms, 50 ms, 100 ms, 500 ms, 1000 ms, 5000 ms). We manipulated board temperature externally by placing the spectroradiometer in the refrigerator one hour prior and then letting the device heat up by itself during the sampling session (~15 to ~36°C, measured by an internal sensor). Corresponding to our experiments, we sampled in 10-sec intervals. Thus, each of the 60-min sessions added up to 360 samples of sensor counts in darkness for every one of the 1024 wavelength pixels measured by the spectroradiometer, plus 360 corresponding board temperature samples. Across all sessions, we collected 2160 raw count samples for each wavelength pixel, along with temperature measurement.

Fig. 2: Variation of dark noise as a function of device temperature and integration time across all wavelengths. Each coloured line indicates the sensor intensity count variation of one specific wavelength pixel in the utilised spectroradiometer (STS-VIS, Ocean Insight Inc., Oxford, UK). Dark- and thermal noise across wavelength pixels increases with higher device temperature. This effect is more pronounced in samples taken with longer integration time (e.g., 1 sec vs. 0.1 sec).

Polynomial Curve Fitting (Training data):

Based on this training dataset, we used the “fit” function of MATLAB’s Curve Fitting Toolbox™ (R2020a, The MathWorks, Inc.) to compute goodness-of-fit statistics from five different polynomial models (1x1, 2x1, 2x2, 3x1, 4x1*, see Tab. 1), iterated across the pixels in the visible wavelength range (847 pixels, 380–780 nm range). For each model, we predicted dark measurement counts [Z in number of sensor counts] from board temperature [X in °C] and integration time [Y in ms]. A summary of the goodness-of-fit statistics across all pixels for the five different polynomial models is displayed in Table 1. Since we use the same raw data (training data) in each model, the “total variance of counts” in a pixel remains the same across all models, which allows us to compare the models via their coefficient of determination statistics.

Model Degree*	Number of coefficients	min R^2_{adj}	med R^2_{adj}	max R^2_{adj}	Number of pixels, $R^2_{adj} < 0.9$
1x1	3	0.108	0.848	0.991	837
2x1	5	0.489	0.990	0.997	18
2x2	6	0.489	0.990	0.997	18
3x1	7	0.572	0.999	0.999	3
3x2	9	0.572	0.999	0.999	3

Table 1: Calibration model selection: Goodness-of-fit statistics for different polynomial models. *The numbers in the notation form “3x1” reflect the degrees of the independent variables used in each model. For instance, “3x1” denotes a model with independent variable X [temperature in °C] used in the third degree (cubic) and independent variable Y [integration time in ms] used in the first degree (linear). R^2_{adj} denotes the coefficient of determination, adjusted for inflation by number of coefficients in the model. Each wavelength pixel in visible range ($n = 847$ pixels) yielded one corresponding R^2_{adj} value for each polynomial model fit. The descriptive statistics for one model are calculated across all 847 pixels.

Model Selection (Training Dataset):

To select the most appropriate polynomial model, descriptive statistics of R^2_{adj} values across all pixels were used as the comparison metric. Generally, the coefficient of determination R^2 is defined as

$$\mathbf{A)} R^2 = 1 - \frac{\text{Unexplained variance}}{\text{Total variance}}$$

In contrast to these R^2 values, which increase by merely raising the number of predictors in a model, R^2_{adj} values are corrected for this inflation effect, by incorporating a term that relates the number of predictors in each respective model to the number of all samples in the dataset [21, 22].

$$\mathbf{B)} R^2_{adj} = 1 - \frac{\text{Unexplained variance} \cdot (P-1)}{\text{Total variance} \cdot (P-p)}$$

Where P denotes the number of samples in the training data set and p the number of coefficients in each respective model.

As demonstrated in Tab. 1 and further visualised by Fig. 2 A and B, meaningful model fit improvements, as reflected by the R^2_{adj} values, were apparent by increasing temperature from a first- (1x1) to a second- (2x1) to a third-degree predictor (3x1). Neither increasing integration time to a second-degree predictor

(2x2) nor raising temperature to a fourth-degree predictor (4x1) led to any additional goodness-of-fit improvements. Consequentially, the polynomial model "3x1" was selected for calibration, yielding the full Formula:

$$\mathbf{C)} Z(X, Y) = p_{00} + p_{10} * X + p_{01} * Y + p_{20} * X^2 + p_{11} * X * Y + p_{30} * X^3 + p_{21} * X^2 * Y$$

where p are the coefficients in the model, X is device temperature [°C], and Y is integration time [ms]

Fig. 3: Calibration model selection: Goodness-of-fit statistics for different polynomial models. **A** The cumulative probability plot illustrates the relative probability (y-axis) that a wavelength pixel in the respective polynomial model (indicated by the lines) takes a value equal to or less than the R^2_{adj} value scaled on the x-axis. The plot indicates the goodness-of-fit improvements from model 1x1 to model 2x1 to model 3x1. **B.** Wavelength dependence of fit quality, contrasting the R^2_{adj} values (y-axis) between model 2x1 (dotted blue line) and 3x1 (red line) across wavelength pixels (x-axis). Pixels with $R^2_{adj} < .9$ are highlighted.

Pixel Selection:

To minimise misestimation in the noise calibration, pixels that showed a high number of residuals in the prediction ("dead pixels"), were identified and excluded in a two-step process. Considering the high wavelength pixel resolution (847 pixels between 380 and 780 nm; ~0.5 nm spacing) and resampling to obtain evenly spaced 1 nm intervals, pixel exclusion at reasonable levels was achieved with minimal loss of information. In both steps, the Root Mean Square Error (*RMSE*) was used as the indicator for absolute deviation between the empirical sensor count in the training data set (Z) and the prediction by the 3x1 model (\hat{Z}). Selecting pixels based on their R^2_{adj} values was not appropriate because these values are computed in proportion to the total variance of sensor counts in each pixel of the raw data (see Formula B). Hence, R^2_{adj} can yield high estimates simply due to large total variance while possibly also showing high residual values, which we want to prevent here. *RMSE* is given by:

$$\mathbf{D)} \text{ } RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Z_i - \hat{Z}_i)^2}{n}}$$

where Z_i is the i^{th} sample of sensor counts in darkness, \hat{Z}_i is the respective value predicted by the 3x1 model and n denotes the number of samples taken for each pixel (in training dataset: $n = 2160$; in validation dataset: $n = 67$)

Pixel Exclusion in Training Dataset:

We aimed to establish an appropriate *RMSE* threshold in the training dataset while keeping data loss due to pixel exclusion in check. Different *RMSE* threshold levels, starting with $RMSE \geq 10$ [sensor counts] were plotted against the resulting number of pixels to exclude in a stepwise 0.25 decrease. As portrayed in Fig. 4 the line, which indicates the "number of pixels to exclude" in the training data, forms an "elbow" illustrating a sharp rise in the number of pixels to exclude when threshold decreases from $RMSE \geq 3.25$ (12 pixels) to $RMSE \geq 3.0$ (31 pixels). Consequently, the 12 pixels in the visible wavelength range with $RMSE \geq 3.25$ in the training dataset were excluded from further analysis.

Pixel Exclusion in Validation Dataset:

Subsequently, the remaining 835 pixels were used to predict noise counts from another 67 dark samples, collected during an early test run of the experiments. The *RMSE* threshold was not set as strictly as before because these samples were collected in a dark room instead of being covered with a plastic cap, all yielding the maximum 5-sec integration time (accompanied by a higher noise rate). Again, *RMSE* values were calculated and inspected by eye to identify

conspicuous pixels. This way, three additional pixels yielding $RMSE > 25$ were tagged and excluded from further analysis.

Fig. 4: Calibration pixel selection: visualisation of wavelength pixel exclusion in training dataset. *RMSE* denotes the Root Mean Square Error. Tightening the threshold beyond $RMSE \geq 3.25$, leads to a sharp rise in the number of pixels to exclude (12 vs. 31 pixels).

Noise Spectra Computation:

In the remaining final 832 wavelength pixels, the seven coefficients (p_{00} to p_{21}) of the (3x1) model according to Formula C were used to predict a “noise count” from board temperature $[X]$ and integration time $[Y]$ samples, corresponding to every light sample in the experiment. The resulting “noise spectra” were subtracted from the empirical spectral samples during data pre-processing, which concluded the calibration process.

4 Evaluation

4.1 Device Set-up

After a first draft, where the spectroradiometer was placed on the side of the head, we upgraded it with a customised 3D-printed case (see Fig. 1) to place it as close to the corneal plane as possible and make it adjustable to a default outdoor gaze angle (15° below the horizontal, [17]). Given the geometry of the sensor and human head, this is the closest we could get to measuring corneal irradiance. The versatile portable set-up can be used in future studies to investigate further pupil size regulation and other biomarkers in relation to

corneal irradiance under real-world conditions and in situations where the circumstances require ambulatory measurements.

4.2 Dark and Thermal Noise Calibration Procedure

The most reliable remedy for dark- and thermal noise in spectroradiometric measurements usually encompasses subtracting corresponding dark samples generated with a shutter mechanism or manual measurements with the cap on. As this is not possible with some small-scale spectroradiometers like the utilised Ocean Insight STS-Vis and not practical in the field, these devices need to be calibrated by software. To develop a calibration model estimating the dark and thermal noise by ourselves, we collected a dark spectra database and used polynomial curve fitting for every wavelength pixel to generate "noise spectra" corresponding to the empirical spectral measurements. Measurements with high integration time (in darkness/ dim light) and high temperature are most susceptible to noise. After the calibration, samples taken in darkness yielded values not exceeding ~1 lux, giving an estimate for the maximum dark- and thermal noise level in our data. For further improvements in noise estimation accuracy, the dark spectra database could be extended to cover more integration time and temperature values. Additionally, one could collect more samples per condition, before applying the model fitting.

5 Conclusion:

In summary, we demonstrate a robust portable system for measuring eye-level light exposure and physiological signals in humans under dynamic real-world conditions, combining an off-the-shelf wearable video-based eye tracker with an off-the-shelf spectroradiometer sampling spectral irradiance in the approximate corneal plane. Testing under dynamic uncontrolled conditions yielded high data retention (~65% data retained; total number of usable spectrum and pupil size pairs: 6620). Finally, we described our successful DIY approach of dark and thermal noise calibration in great detail. In the future, this set-up will be used to address real-world light and pupil assessment in a wide range of research questions and use-cases.

6 References

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